

Skills 4 eosc

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
- Commons

Supporting | eosc

Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
UK Research
and Innovation

Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres

Version 1.0

Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres

Version 1.0 (January 2025)

Authors

Agnes Jasinska, DCC

Lottie Provost, CNR

Betty Evangelinou,
GRNET

Emma Lazzeri, GARR

Fotis Mystakopoulos,
OPERAS

Daniel Turner, DCC

George Psathas, GRNET

Design

[Aedeka Srl](#)

Images & icons

[Adobe Stock](#), [Freepik](#),
[Flaticon](#).

Disclaimer

This is a digest of Deliverable “**D3.4 Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres**” (<https://zenodo.org/records/14538239>) and was produced by the Skills4EOSC project. The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].

The information and views set out in this document are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission guarantees the accuracy of the information included in this document. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on the European Commission’s behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Copyright Notice

This work by Parties of the Skills4EOSC Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License: creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0

DOI link

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14751412>

Summary

The Science4Policy Kit, developed by Skills4EOSC Task 3.3, is a practical resource offering real-life examples of Science4Policy initiatives, providing a rich repository of diverse case studies for Competence Centres to include in training activities, or to inspire similar initiatives in their local contexts. The Science4Policy Kit was created using a dual approach combining landscaping and survey methodologies to gather data on Science4Policy initiatives across multiple countries. These initiatives were categorised into ten distinct types, with representative examples featured in the Science4Policy Kit, highlighting practical tools and successful methodologies which serve as an inspiration for integrating science into policy-making processes.

Initiatives Types

Science advisor to the government

A single permanent position or an office with several staff members who provide advice to policy makers and decision makers in the government. This could be science advice as well as technology advice, and in some cases, both.

A network of scientists to advise the government

A network of scientists who can provide advice to policy makers and decision makers in the government. This could be science advice, technology advice, or both combined. The network could be national, international, or global.

Evidence synthesis

Regular or ad hoc reports that summarise scientific evidence in a specific field or on a specific topic. These reports can be generated by scientists and delivered to policy makers and decision makers in the government on a regular schedule. They could also be commissioned by the government in response to specific new issues or developments.

Academic centres for science and policy

Academic centres for science and policy serve as knowledge and community hubs. They conduct research, offer academic degree programs and professional development opportunities related to science for policy, as well as create and disseminate resources, organise annual conferences and other community-building events, and host professional networks.

Policy training for scientists (and science training for policy-makers)

A variety of policy fellowships and internships can provide a training opportunity for scientists or science trainees to gain knowledge, skills, and experience related to policy making. Typically, the focus of the training is on the policy-making process and on using scientific evidence and expertise to inform this process and the resulting policies.

Initiatives Types

Science-policy pairing schemes

Scientists are paired with policy-makers for a specific period of time (a week, a month, a year) and in a specific format (e.g., fully in-person, online with in-person visits, fully online). The goal is for the scientist to gain first-hand knowledge of policy-making process and policy-makers' needs, while also contributing their scientific expertise as needed.

Science for policy conferences and other community-building events

Conferences and other similar events devoted to the intersection and integration of science and policy are a powerful means of bringing together professionals active in both science and policy.

Science (and science for policy) media

One approach to fostering science for policy is to support and improve science communication. These initiatives could take the form of a specific science publication or a science media hub. The goal is to present reliable and up-to-date scientific information in a clear and non-technical language that is understandable to non-specialists. Science journalists and science journal publishers are often a critical partner in these initiatives.

Academia-government partnerships

A formal partnership between an academic institution and the local government can be a powerful way to integrate science and policy with the aim of generating science-based policy solutions to the challenges facing the region.

Science for policy hackathons

Science for policy hackathons are short, intense collaborations between scientists and policy-makers focused on tackling real-life problems and generating science-based solutions to complex societal issues such as climate change. These hackathons are often organised and hosted by a university and involve students as well as scientists and policy-makers.

Featured Initiatives

Initiative Type	Initiative Name	Country	Page
Science advisor to the government	Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques (OPECST)	France	7
A network of scientists to advise the government	International Network for Governmental Science Advice (INGSA)	Australia, Global	8
	Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM) to the European Commission	European	9
Evidence synthesis	European Marine Board – Future Science Brief No.11 'Marine habitat mapping'	Belgium	10
Academic centres for science and policy	The Rathenau Instituut	The Netherlands	11
	Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge	UK	12
Policy training for scientists (and science training for policy-makers)	Erasmus+ Project: ENGAGEgreen – Enhancing Institutional Capacities for Policy Engagement for Green and Digital Transitions	Germany	13
Science-policy pairing schemes	European Geosciences Union (EGU) Science-Policy Pairing Scheme	Germany	14
	SIMIL II: Science-Policy Dialogue on WATER	Spain	15
Science for policy conferences and other community-building events	Data for Policy Conference Series	UK	16
Science (and science for policy) media	Scienza in Rete	Italy	17
Academia-government partnerships	Impronta Granada	Brazil	18
Science for policy hackathons	Science for Policy Hackathon	Austria	19

Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques

WEBSITE: <https://www.senat.fr/travaux-parlementaires/office-et-delegations/office-parlementaire-devaluation-des-choix-scientifiques-et-technologiques.html>

DESCRIPTION

The Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques (OPECST) is a joint information body of the French National Assembly and Senate, and was created by a law in 1983. Made up of 18 deputies and 18 senators, the Office's mission, under the terms of the law, is 'to inform Parliament of the consequences of scientific and technological choices in order, in particular, to inform its decisions'. It therefore provides Parliament with the expertise it needs to make long-term political choices.

COUNTRY: France

SCOPE: National

STATUS: Ongoing

SIMILAR INITIATIVES

Similar Offices are present in several European countries and are often part of the European Parliamentary Technology Assessment network (<https://eptanetwork.org/index.php>).

- The Office of Technology Assessment at the German Bundestag (TAB), Germany, <https://www.tab-beim-bundestag.de/english/index.php>
- The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology (POST), United Kingdom, <https://post.parliament.uk/about-us/>

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Science advice to government can also take the form of independent citizen initiatives which aim to make the formulation of political proposals science-based.

- Ciencia en el Parlamento, Spain, <https://cienciaenelparlamento.org>
- Scienza in Parlamento, Italy, <https://www.scienzainparlamento.org/>

A network of scientists
to advise the government

FEATURED INITIATIVE

International Network for Governmental Science Advice (INGSA)

WEBSITE: <https://ingsa.org/>

DESCRIPTION

The International Network for Governmental Science Advice (INGSA) is a collaborative platform for policy exchange, capacity building, and research across diverse global science advisory organisations and national systems. Through workshops, conferences and a growing catalogue of tools and guidance, the network aims to enhance the global knowledge-to-policy interface to improve the potential for evidence-informed policy formation at sub-national, national and transnational levels.

There are many opportunities for organisations or individuals to collaborate with INGSA – from skill-building internships to partnerships.

INGSA works via a decentralised governance model, allowing for an interconnected and diverse ecosystem of networks.

COUNTRY:

Multiple countries

SCOPE:

Global

STATUS:

Ongoing

SIMILAR INITIATIVES

At the European level, similar initiatives provide advice to policy makers and decision makers in the government.

- European Geosciences Union Science for Policy Working Group, <https://www.egu.eu/structure/committees-and-working-groups/policy/>
- Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/stoa/en/home/>

A network of scientists
to advise the government

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Scientific Advice Mechanism to the European Commission

Website: <https://scientificadvice.eu/>

DESCRIPTION

The Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM) to the European Commission provides independent scientific evidence and policy recommendations to the College of European Commissioners on any subject, including on policy issues that the European Parliament and the Council consider to be of major importance.

The process used by the Scientific Advice Mechanism to the EU follows these steps:

1. Policy-maker submits a request for advice on a specific topic or issue.
2. A working group of experts reviews evidence and writes an evidence review report.
3. A separate group of advisors writes a document with recommendations based on the evidence.
4. The evidence report and the recommendations are both delivered to the policy-maker.

COUNTRY:

Multiple countries

SCOPE: European

STATUS: Ongoing

FEATURED INITIATIVE

European Marine Board - Future Science Brief No.11 'Marine habitat mapping'

WEBSITE: <https://www.marineboard.eu/publications/marine-habitat-mapping>

DESCRIPTION

This Future Science Brief highlights science and policy needs and recommendations to advance marine habitat mapping in order to fulfil European and international ambitions for biodiversity, conservation, restoration and climate. It covers the following overarching topics:

1. Collecting data for marine habitat mapping: current and future trends in collecting remotely sensed data and direct, in situ observations, and integrating artificial intelligence.
2. Combining data to produce marine habitat maps: physical and biological habitat maps, distribution models, fit-for-purpose habitat classification schemes, and assessing and communicating accuracy and confidence.
3. What and where to map: what has been mapped, key gaps, the need for spatial prioritisation, who uses marine habitat maps and for what purpose, and bespoke fit-for-purpose maps.
4. Communication and dissemination: increasing the value of each map via data dissemination, and using marine habitat maps to improve public understanding of the Ocean.

COUNTRY: Belgium

SCOPE: International

STATUS: Completed

QUOTE FROM SURVEY RESPONDENT

“Personal contacts within policy can help to establish important stakeholder contacts, and good communication and facilitation in a working group of diverse expertise is key.”

“The document was written by 14 experts from across Europe and highlights the current trends and future needs in science and policy to advance marine habitat mapping, which is needed to help deliver the ambitious plans of the European Green Deal of scaling-up blue economy activities and simultaneously protecting and restoring marine ecosystems as part of the EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy and the newly approved EU Nature Restoration Law.”

FEATURED INITIATIVE

The Rathenau Instituut

Website: <https://www.rathenau.nl/en>

DESCRIPTION

Since 1986, the Rathenau Instituut has been conducting research and organising public dialogue on the impact of science, technology, and innovation on society. They also concern themselves with developments in science, technology, and innovation in such areas as the sustainable supply of energy, the agricultural transition, and socially responsible digitalisation.

COUNTRY:

The Netherlands

SCOPE: International

STATUS: Ongoing

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

An academic centre can create and manage multiple other initiatives with a regional, national, or international scope. Note that the centre may study policy-making and governance more broadly, with science-based and evidence-based policies being only one aspect of the work. Alternatively, the centre may focus on a specific aspect of evidence-based policy, such as the use of open data in policy-making.

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), University of Cambridge

WEBSITE: <https://www.csap.cam.ac.uk/>

DESCRIPTION

The mission of the Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP) is to improve policy making through the more effective use of evidence and expertise. Since the launch in 2009, the CSaP has pioneered a particular approach to bringing science and policy together. They forge relationships based on mutual understanding and trust, and build networks of people with shared values of intellectual curiosity and public service. From that starting point, they curate open and exploratory conversations to address public policy.

The CSaP offers:

1. Policy fellowships
2. Events focussed on topics of strategic importance to research and policy
3. Policy workshops connecting academics to policy makers
4. Professional development for researchers interested in making a transition to a scientific advisor
5. The CSaP network of academics and policy makers that spans all disciplines
6. Help with planning for policy engagement and increasing the policy impact of academic research

COUNTRY: UK

SCOPE: International

STATUS: Ongoing

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Erasmus+ Project: ENGAGEgreen - Enhancing Institutional Capacities for Policy Engagement for Green and Digital Transitions

WEBSITE: https://www.uni-frankfurt.de/148433721/Project_Summary

DESCRIPTION

ENGAGEgreen seeks to enhance researchers' knowledge, skills, and competencies for policy engagement, thereby supporting effective knowledge transfer for evidence-informed policy-making in the areas of environment, fight against climate change, and digital transformation. Additionally, the project will strengthen universities' institutional capacities of policy engagement as they will be able to offer innovative trainings in these areas for researchers, students, and research managers.

COUNTRY: Germany

SCOPE: National

STATUS: Ongoing

QUOTES FROM SURVEY RESPONDENT

"The idea is about fostering policy engagement in different local and national settings and learning from each other."

"The consortium is very diverse in terms of involved disciplines, type of activities, and resources."

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

These training opportunities are often intended for postgraduate trainees or early-career researchers, but might be open to all ranks as well. They typically involve a placement of the policy fellow or intern in a policy making context for a specific period of time (e.g., three months). In some cases, policy training for scientists can be combined with science training for policy-makers, which facilitates a dialogue between the two groups and helps to build trust and collaboration.

FEATURED INITIATIVE

European Geosciences Union (EGU) Science-Policy Pairing Scheme

Website: <https://www.egu.eu/policy/pairing-schemes/>

DESCRIPTION

The annual Science–Policy Pairing Scheme sponsored by the European Geosciences Union (EGU) aims to promote a culture of evidence–informed policymaking and encourage stronger science–policy partnerships.

The scheme offers selected Europe–based EGU members the opportunity to gain insights into the policymaking process and the types of information policymakers need while at the same time providing policymakers with access to scientific expertise. As part of the scheme, selected EGU members visit Brussels and work alongside a Member of the European Parliament (MEP) who has volunteered to participate in this scheme. All expenses are covered by the EGU. The dates and specific activities are determined by each MEP’s needs, the area of expertise of the selected scientist and the participants’ availability.

COUNTRY: Germany

SCOPE: International

STATUS: Ongoing

QUOTES FROM SURVEY RESPONDENT

“Since 2019, the EGU has been pairing 1–2 researchers with a Member of the European Parliament, enabling them to work with the MEP and their team inside the European Parliament in Brussels for up to a week. This pairing scheme aims to enable the researcher to better understand policymakers’ needs and how legislation is passed in the Parliament while encouraging MEPs and their teams to consider consulting with researchers and using scientific information to support their decision–making.”

“We tried one pairing during COVID which was online. And the feedback from both sides was less positive as it was harder to form a connection.”

FEATURED INITIATIVE

SIMIL II: Science-Policy Dialogue on WATER

Website: <https://simil.cat/en>

DESCRIPTION

The SIMIL programme pairs scientists with political representatives in order to provide independent scientific support for the development of public policies at the local and regional levels. The goal is to utilise scientific knowledge to find evidence-based solutions to the specific problems and challenges of the region.

The SIMIL programme consists of:

- In-person sessions with researchers to identify challenges, exchange knowledge, and build trust.
- Several work sessions, both in-person and virtual, to jointly create solutions.
- In-person visits to learn about the initiatives successfully implemented in the field in the current edition of the SIMIL programme.
- Continuous monitoring and direct communication between researchers and scientists.
- A final event where conclusions are presented and a technical report is delivered to aid decision-making.

COUNTRY: Spain

SCOPE: Regional

STATUS: Ongoing

Science for policy conferences
and other community-building events

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Data for Policy Conference Series

WEBSITE: <https://dataforpolicy.org/about-us/>

DESCRIPTION

Data for Policy is a leading global community dedicated to fostering a beneficial discourse on the impact and potential of data, AI, and related technologies in government, governance, and policy. The Data for Policy network consists of over 5000 experts globally, actively shaping and enriching the transdisciplinary and cross-sector dialogue.

Following six successful global conferences in the UK, the Data for Policy Conference Series expanded to include regional editions in 2022. This strategic move allows a balance between global conversations and networking, while also capturing the diverse regional contexts of data for policy research worldwide.

COUNTRY: UK

SCOPE: International

STATUS: Ongoing

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Policy conferences and similar events provide an entry into the field for trainees and early-career professionals, as well as ongoing professional development for more senior practitioners (including policy training for scientists, science training for policy makers, and the skills and tools necessary for integrating scientific evidence into policy making and decision making). Regular conferences (e.g., annual) are also instrumental in building a community of practice around science and policy, fostering mutual trust and facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration.

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Scienza in Rete (SCIRE)

Website: <https://www.scienzainrete.it/>

DESCRIPTION

Scienza in Rete is a journal of current affairs and scientific culture. It aims to inform the public debate with journalism based on knowledge and the scientific method, giving a voice to researchers. To do this, the editorial staff serves as a “cultural mediator” between the world of research and society to offer the public clear and useful tools for understanding what is happening.

COUNTRY: Italy

SCOPE: National

STATUS: Ongoing

SIMILAR INITIATIVES

At the European level, similar initiatives bring scientists, journalists and policymakers together with the aim to support and improve science communication.

- European Science-Media Hub,
<https://sciencemediahub.eu/>
- European Geosciences Union GeoPolicy blog,
<https://blogs.egu.eu/geolog/category/geopolicy/>

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Impronta Granada

Website: <https://improntagranada.es/que-es-impronta-granada/>

DESCRIPTION

Impronta Granada is an alliance between the University of Granada and the Provincial Council of Granada that aims to address the challenges of the province and its municipalities by establishing a creative and productive dialogue, knowledge exchange, and collaboration between the various institutions and social actors in the province.

COUNTRY: Spain

SCOPE: Regional

STATUS: Ongoing

QUOTES FROM SURVEY RESPONDENT

“The initiative emerged from the need to create a systematic framework for connecting the university with the surrounding region through municipalities and the Diputación de Granada (provincial council).”

“The importance of collaboration and interpersonal relationships between team members at the university and between the university and the Diputación of Granada is fundamental to the project’s success, as it enables synergy between both institutions. In many cases, personal calls have facilitated joint work, with one institution integrating into activities organised by the other, thus generating value for both institutions.”

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Academia–government partnership can stimulate a mutual exchange of knowledge needed to address the problems, as well as provide a meeting space and a structure for dialogue and collaboration. They enable a range of activities, such as consultancy, advocacy, project preparation, and challenge–based learning and research. Overall, they can have a transformative impact on the community and the region.

FEATURED INITIATIVE

Science for Policy Hackathon

DESCRIPTION

In the Science for Policy Hackathon, students and early-career researchers collaborate in interdisciplinary teams to tackle real-world policy challenges, applying their skills and expertise to develop science-based solutions for societal issues like climate change and biodiversity.

The goal of this science for policy hackathon is to encourage students and early-career researchers to apply their expertise and skills in a real-world policy context of the City of Vienna. Participants gain an in-depth understanding of the development of science-based policies in general and relevant structures and processes within the City. All teams are supported by an expert in research-based policy-making.

COUNTRY: Austria

SCOPE: National

STATUS: Ongoing

QUOTE FROM SURVEY RESPONDENT

"We strongly believe in the positive impact of the initiative – for all stakeholders involved."

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

One key benefit of science for policy hackathons is simply bringing scientists and policy-makers together and facilitating their collaboration on pressing issues. Another important benefit is the learning experience for students, who gain valuable first-hand knowledge of how science-based policies are developed.

Good Practices

The following collection of good practices has been gathered from the initiatives analysed. This practical information highlights the key factors underpinning successful Science4Policy efforts, offering clear advice and useful insights to improve and support future initiatives.

COMMUNICATION

Regular Communication & Collaboration Across Diverse Stakeholders:

Regular communication between all partners via meetings and one-on-one interactions is essential. Recognise and adapt to varying levels of expertise among partners while being open to new ideas.

PLANNING & COORDINATION

Thorough Planning & Early Stakeholder Coordination:

Initiatives require early and thorough planning, as well as careful coordination with all stakeholders, to ensure alignment and efficient execution.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Involvement of Policymakers & Scientists through Interaction and Preparation: Bring scientists and policymakers together to foster mutual understanding. Provide resources like FAQ lists and guides to help both parties prepare for meaningful interactions.

INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

Institutionalise Programs for Long-Term Sustainability:

Ensure initiatives are supported at the institutional level for long-term sustainability. Combining top-down and bottom-up approaches allows for enduring programs that are embedded within existing structures.

FLEXIBILITY & ADAPTATION

Adaptation to Feedback & Agile Approach:

It is important to be adaptable to feedback and open to changing approaches based on new insights or challenges. An agile methodology allows for experimentation and fine-tuning of programs.

Good Practices

EMPOWERMENT & CAPACITY BUILDING

Empower Participants & Build Capacity:

Empower participants by making them active contributors to the process. Capacity building initiatives should be in place to ensure that participants feel equipped to contribute and grow within the initiative.

MONITORING & EVALUATION

Regular Evaluation & Adjustment of Activities:

Regularly assess the effectiveness of activities and make necessary adjustments based on feedback or changes in the environment. This ensures ongoing relevance and impact.

INNOVATION

Promote Innovative & Collaborative Programs:

Encourage innovation through collaborative programs such as innovation labs, workshops, and joint projects. This fosters new ideas to tackle challenges from diverse perspectives.

BUILDING RELATIONSHIPS

Build Personal Relationships & Networks:

Building strong personal connections within policymaking and scientific communities facilitates cooperation and trust. This is especially important for securing ongoing collaboration and engagement.

KNOWLEDGE DISSEMINATION

Disseminate Knowledge through Events & Recognition:

Share knowledge gained from the initiative through events, public talks, and recognition of achievements. Highlight success stories and lessons learned to inspire others.

DIVERSITY & INCLUSION

Promote Diverse Participation & Inclusivity:

Encourage participation from a wide range of stakeholders, ensuring inclusivity in terms of background, expertise, and perspective. This helps ensure the initiative is representative and addresses diverse needs.

Skills 4 eosc

www.skills4eosc.eu

in X zenodo

Supporting

Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
UK Research
and Innovation

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].